

ADVANTAGES OF USING ACTIVITIES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Annotation. This article is about using games in teaching English. A lot of games are given with their instruction to use at the English lesson.

Key words: games, using, a lot of, primary, develop, interest, activity, provide
We all know that in primary classes, the foundations of knowledge, skills and practical skills that are necessary for further education are laid. Moral qualities are formed, children's ability to master knowledge independently, and their interest in learning and creative search is aroused.

In my opinion, one of the most effective ways to develop interest in the subject along with other methods and techniques that are used in the classroom, is the game. Games should provide the formation of work skills and the formation of their own training activities. During the game, conditions are created for the development of social roles. The use of educational games makes it possible to think actively, developing creative abilities while completing tasks, to develop the abilities inherent in the child's nature. There are a huge number of games that will help any English teacher diversify their lesson and make it more interesting. I want to present some of them that I have been using in my lessons for years.

One of the best moments in the game is when the child gets a surprise. What if it's a surprise assignment? Recently, I quite often began to use kinder surprises in my practice, or rather eggs from kinder. Inside the eggs, you can hide any word or sentence that needs to be translated. You can also hide grammar tasks. Any child will be happy to take a surprise and look at what is in it, trying to cope with the task.

Activity 1. Alphabet from A to Z.

Throwing the ball, students one by one call the letters of the alphabet from A to Z. If the child is lost, he is eliminated from the game. By naming letters of the alphabet from A to Z, students add a phrase with a word to their letter: "A is for Apple", " B is for Ball".

Activity 2. Game with flapper-flyswatters

In another interesting game, I involve children in the process of learning words with the help of a game with flapper-flyswatters. In advance on the Board, I write the words in different order from the required topic. I

call two students to the blackboard and give them flyswatters. The point of the game is that when the teacher calls a word, students must quickly find it on the Board and slap it. The winner is the one who slapped the most words (if the words on the Board are written in Uzbek, the teacher pronounces them in English and Vice versa).

Activity 3. Game "Calendar".

Of course, you cannot do without more standard, but no less interesting games with cards. For example, the game "Calendar". The teacher in the classroom puts up numbers from one to seven, which indicate the ordinal number of the day of the week. Seven students receive cards with the days of the week written on them. Students' task: stand in front of the number that defines the day of the week. Each child names the day of the week on their cards.

Activity 4. "Appearance". Students are offered an unfamiliar image on the topic "Appearance", such as a portrait of a boy. The children take turns describing his features, clothing, and character. Everyone has the right to say only one sentence. The task will be more exciting if the teacher takes a portrait of a famous person.

Activity 5. "Step by step"

In my classes, children often ask for a "Step by step" game. This game is for checking new words. Students should stand away from the teacher. Then the teacher sets a word (for example: Board games). The one who first correctly translates board games, will take a step towards the teacher, if the student does not know the word, he stands still. The winner is the one who reaches the teacher faster.

Activity 6. Snowball"

I can't help but think of the game "Snowball", which I use both in the Junior and middle levels. One student utters the phrase: I see a pen. The next student repeats this phrase and adds another word: I see a pen and a textbook. The winner is the one who names the most items in the order in which the children named them. And you can also conduct this game with the help of images.

During games, we must remember that the game should make children think and be active. Waiting a long time for your turn to be included in the game reduces interest in it. The material that is used during the game should be easy to use. If several games are played in a lesson, we should alternate between light and heavy games.

In conclusion, for a student, the game is an interesting, exciting interaction with the teacher and peers, in which statements of a certain type are dictated by the internal needs of the game. Of course, we should not forget that playing in a foreign language class is not just a collective entertainment, but the main way to achieve certain learning tasks at this stage-from the smallest speech skills to the ability to conduct an independent conversation.

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